

Understanding Negative Contingencies in Process Mining (PM) Initiatives

• Definition of Contingency

- In Information Systems (IS), a contingency is any condition or factor that affects the potential for achieving value from an implementation.
- Contingencies can be positive or negative and are influenced by an organization's unique environment.
- This work focuses on **negative contingencies**.

• Difference from Critical Success Factors (CSFs)

- Unlike CSFs, contingencies do not directly determine success or failure; they shape value realization by enabling or constraining outcomes.
- Organizations often do not control contingencies but can work to minimize negative impacts or enhance positive effects.

Understanding Negative Contingencies in Process Mining (PM) Initiatives

- **Why Contingencies Matter?**
 - **Organizational Fit:** Show how specific conditions affect IS implementation, highlighting the need to understand unique contexts.
 - **Risk and Resource Management:** Help in identifying risks and ensuring resources are allocated strategically for better preparation and adaptability.
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Negative Contingencies Example in IS

- Inconsistent Data Entry in Customer Relationship Management (CRM) System
 - **Description:** Poor data quality can arise from inconsistent data entry, outdated information, or missing data, all of which can undermine customer insights.
 - **Why it is defined as contingency?** While organizations can implement training, validation mechanisms, and data management policies, variability in data sources and human behavior makes it challenging to ensure consistently high data quality. Poor data quality can hinder the effectiveness of CRM systems, leading to unreliable customer insights and decision-making
 - Lack of Cybersecurity Policies
 - **Description:** Without robust cybersecurity policies, IS are vulnerable to unauthorized access, data breaches, and cyberattacks, putting sensitive customer information at risk.
 - **Why It Is Defined as a Contingency?** Even with policies in place, evolving cyber threats and differing employee awareness levels make it hard to ensure full security. Weak cybersecurity can result in data breaches, legal issues, and loss of customer trust, weakening the IS's system effectiveness
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Objective of the Interview

We have compiled a list of 9 negative contingencies in process mining (PM) implementation

Our objective is to:

- 1) Verify the existence and relevance of the negative contingencies identified and explore other potential negative contingencies based on the expert's experiences
 - 2) To gather insights on how practitioners perceive and manage the identified negative contingencies in PM projects.
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Negative Contingencies in Process Mining

- 1) Distributed Team
 - 2) Result Expectation
 - 3) Data Privacy
 - 4) IOT Data Problem
 - 5) Disconnection between Insight and Improvement
 - 6) Sharing Success Story
 - 7) Organization Alignment
 - 8) Hidden Task
 - 9) Architecture Integration Choices
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1. Distributed Team

Definition	Case Study Example
<p>The condition in which the company uses BPM and PM teams from different departments, regions, or even different countries. The diversity of the people involved may require deep technical and/or cultural adaptation.</p>	<p>Company A started a process mining (PM) project with a team spread across multiple countries, corresponding to the locations of different business units. This setup introduced challenges due to structural and cultural differences among the teams. For example, the development authority was based in one country, while component responsibilities were assigned to teams in another.</p> <p>To ensure smooth collaboration, the teams had to align on data structure, consistency, and completeness, as well as manage varying work habits and interpretations of key terms in process mining.</p>

2. Results Expectation

Definition	Case Study Examples
<p>The condition in which the company has too high expectations from a PM tool based on industry rumours/advertising. Too high expectations may lead to unnecessary organizational adaptation to meet the promises and increased pressure for the PM staff.</p>	<p>Company B decided to pilot their Procure to Pay (PTP) process with a German software provider known for good ERP integration and a user-friendly experience. They chose this provider because it had successfully worked with a major competitor. However, there were high expectations for the tool, and a lot of adjustments were necessary when starting the process mining project.</p> <p>Additionally, the other case study highlighted that a lack of process standardization across business units complicates transformation efforts. Customizing processes to meet specific business needs has led to deviations from ERP standards, making it difficult to migrate systems. Ultimately, there is no one-size-fits-all solution.</p>

3. Data Privacy

Definition	Case Study Example
<p>The condition in which the need to comply with data protection laws and regulations poses serious challenges in data management and storage in PM projects. This contingency can increase complexity of PM particularly in global organizations, where differing local regulations must be navigated and consistently upheld.</p>	<p>Company C encountered significant challenges related to data security and privacy, especially when implementing cloud-based use cases for Human Resources (HR) and Service processes. Ensuring compliance with regulations like General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) was crucial to avoid complications regarding the use of process customer or staff data.</p> <p>Another case study highlighted the importance of following GDPR from the beginning. Meeting data privacy requirements takes significant effort, as companies need to balance regulations with effective data management for analysis.</p>

4. IOT Data Problem

Definition	Case Study Example
<p>The condition in which a large part of the data required by PM is generated by the Internet of Things (IoT), e.g., sensors. IoT data are often generated in large size and volume, unstructured and not standardized. This can make it challenging to extract meaningful event logs, requiring significant data transformation to enable PM analysis.</p>	<p>Company D faced challenges with unstructured IoT data, as event logs from IoT devices often require significant processing to be usable for process mining. In a pilot project, they collaborated with consultants to standardize and prepare Computed Tomography (CT) scanner data for analysis.</p> <p>An example from another case study underscores this complexity, as extracting event logs from IoT scenarios demands intensive analysis due to the non-standardized nature of the data.</p>

5. Disconnection between insight and improvement

Definition	Case Study Example
<p>The condition in which an organization struggles to translate the insights obtained from PM into actionable and measurable business process improvements, due to e.g. lack of integration of PM with operational systems or organizational resistance. In this situation, the importance of PM may remain hidden to many stakeholders, leading PM initiatives to be less supported over time.</p>	<p>Company E enhanced used PM to identify key process improvement areas, but the actual changes had to be implemented outside of the PM tools—in ERP systems or organizational structures. This highlights the risk of information paralysis, as it can take time for teams to translate insights from PM into actions that impact governance and business value.</p> <p>An example from the other case study shows that pairing analysis with concrete actions and AI-driven automations can accelerate value realization and improve user buy-in, making it easier to demonstrate the benefits of PM.</p>

6. Sharing Success Story

Definition	Case Study Example
<p>The condition in which PM success stories and best practices communicated across different teams and departments lead to such teams to simply mimic the successful use cases, without adapting the successful use cases to the specific characteristics of the local context to avoid misalignment or unrealistic expectations.</p>	<p>Company F's CoE (Center of Excellence) shared best practices across regions and business units, expecting each team to adopt them based on local needs. However, some teams might implement these practices directly, without adjusting them to their unique business conditions. The teams that used PM to identify specific insights, implement those, and return to PM to gather the evidence about where process improvements were visible, were more likely to show successful outcomes.</p> <p>The one-size-fits-all approach could reduce the effectiveness of the implementations, as it fails to consider specific local contexts.</p>

7. Organizational Alignment

Definition	Case Study Example
<p data-bbox="86 505 449 537">Organizational Alignment</p> <p data-bbox="86 589 779 829">Ensuring that all stakeholders, departments, and teams are aligned with the goals of the PM initiative. This includes having shared objectives, understanding roles, and establishing ownership, which can be a time-consuming process.</p>	<p data-bbox="800 505 1955 662">Company B spent about a year stabilizing their Center of Excellence (CoE), facing challenges with onboarding, establishing procedures, and managing international collaboration. Building skills and ensuring team alignment took time, as training alone doesn't immediately translate to results.</p> <p data-bbox="800 716 1955 873">Setting up a CoE for process transformation requires substantial effort, involving stakeholder engagement and fostering a sense of ownership across teams. It's a gradual process to ensure that process intelligence is valued beyond existing data and analytics initiatives.</p>

8. Hidden Task

Definition	Case Study Example
<p>The condition in which several key actions or tasks in the business processes targeted by PM are not recorded, such as manual interventions or activities conducted in non-integrated systems. These tasks can create blind spots in PM analysis and affect the overall quality of the insights extracted using PM.</p>	<p>Company G encountered challenges with hidden tasks—user actions that aren't captured by logging mechanisms, such as manual tasks or those performed outside the main software. These tasks can emerge at any stage of PM and may result from project prioritization or scope limitations.</p>

9. Architecture Integration Choice

Definition	Case Study Example
<p>The condition in which decisions regarding how PM solutions are integrated into the organization's existing IT infrastructure influence which data can be collected for PM and, therefore, the quality of PM insights. Factors such as compatibility, scalability, and the need for customization of PM solutions to the existing IT landscape may impact the long-term viability and cost of PM.</p>	<p>After using process mining (PM) for three years, Company B has learned some key lessons. A primary recommendation for organizations starting their PM journey is to plan their system architecture early. Cloud solutions for example offering key benefit.</p> <p>As the project progresses, adjustments may be necessary, potentially requiring more resources over time. Additionally, gaps in knowledge or indirect outcomes can add to costs. Thus, making wise choices in system integration is crucial to achieving long-term impact.</p>

Key Questions

The interview will have several key questions as follows:

- Part 1: Understanding Negative Contingencies
 - Contingency Concept Familiarity
 - Specific Negative Contingencies
 - Managing Negative Contingencies

 - Part 2: Other Negative Contingencies
 - Part 3: Distinguishing from Critical Success Factors
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